

Study of Efficacy of Some Non-leguminous Plant Extracts On *Spodoptera litura*

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Abstract

The tropical neem tree (*Azadirachta indica*), has lots of medicinal and pesticide properties. Virtually each and every section of the *Azadirachta* tree has also been used by means of indigenous cultures for remedy or pest manipulation for over 2050 years. Neem oil extracts are normally used to deal with a variety of infections and repellent for insects. In the study effects of neem extracts was once evaluated towards eggs and 2nd instar larva of the tropical army worm *S. litura* (regarded as a leaf worm). We conclude that neem oil extracts killed 98.2 % of eggs and 99% of larvae, pupa and adult moth of *spodoptera* uncovered to extracts of *Azadirachta* leaves, because neem leaf extracts are no longer dangerous to plant life or humans. These chemical substances can be used to manage many types of insects in farm and round dwellings.

Keywords Spodoptera, Azadirachta Indica, Extracts, Pesticides, Culture.

Introduction

Azadirachta indica and *Ocimum sanctum* plant

Neem tree (*Azadirachta indica*) is a quickly developing evergreen tree frequent in dry tropical regions. Azadirachtin, a product derived from *Azadirachta indica*, is used in many components of the world in functions ranging from the remedy of belly ulcers to cosmetics. Neem extracts are poisonous to many insects however no longer to human beings or plants, and even physique cleaning soap and toothpaste can be discovered that comprise fabric from neem leaves. Neem leaves are additionally used to deal with leprosy, eye disorders, intestinal worms, pores and skin ulcers, cardiovascular disease, diabetes, fever, gingivitis, and liver problems. *Azadirachta* extracts, which can be made from the whole plant, repel insects except destructive the crop itself. Amid developing worries about the poisonous residue that artificial chemical pesticides can go away on plants, many farmers have commenced to use neem extracts as a naturally going on pesticide with blow toxicity on humans. These extracts have a variety of organic results on insects, pathogens, plant parasitic nematodes, and arachnids, and have additionally been said to be poisonous to all insect life-stages, inflicting both mortality or bodily abnormalities.

A range of business formulations of neem extracts are available. *Spodoptera litura* (Fabricius) the frequent cutworm is an economically vital noctuid moth which is a polyphagous pest inflicting sizeable financial loss to many veggies and area plants the most important ones being tobacco, cotton, rice, maize, cabbage, lettuce, tea etc. It is capable to wreck a vegetable crop and in particular prefers greens inside cabbage family. Management of *Spodoptera litura* (Fabricius) populace the use of artificial pesticides has proved futile as it has developed resistance to various instructions of insecticides. Moreover an expanded attention of achievable risks of artificial pesticides as nicely as a everlasting amplify in pest resistance, resurgence, residual toxicity, and surroundings deterioration etc. in the course of previous three many years has led the scientists to take a look at the opportunity of the use of much less persistent, biodegradable, and in your price range and ecofriendly choices which include plant-derived insecticides. The tobacco worm can shortly unfold in the course of the crop if it has an appropriate environment.

Spodoptera litura has been mentioned to assault 112 plant species belonging to forty four families, of which forty species are regarded from India. *Spodoptera litura* has proven resistance towards all the insecticidal agencies which includes the newly synthesized lufenuron. Plants are the storehouse of a extensive array of bioactive chemical compounds that are used in defence towards herbivores. These bio pesticides, which are in the main alkaloids, steroids, phenolic, tannins and many others can manage pest due to their more than one modes of action. These chemicals are deleterious to insects in a couple of ways, such as via acute toxicity, affecting insect behavior, disrupting boom and improvement of worms and performing as repellents, antifeedants and oviposition deterrents. The use of botanical pesticides for defending vegetation from insect pests has assumed notable significance in current years. Numerous plant species have been stated to possess pest manipulate houses however solely a few of them have been correctly registered as an insecticide in latest years.

The plant-based pesticides exhibit variable impact towards special insect species. Thus in the current scenario, the discovering of precise plant-based pesticides is inevitable and is need of the hour. In the current find out about the ovicidal impact of leaf extracts of *Azadirachta indica* and *Ocimum sanctum* and seed extract of neem tree leaves used to be evaluated towards *Spodoptera litura*.

Objective of study

The main objective of this research paper is to study the efficacy of extracts of some non-leguminous plants on *Spodoptera litura*.

Review of Literature

According to Sahayraj and Paulraj (1998) The cutworm *Spodoptera litura* Fab. (Lepidoptera, Noctudae) is well known as a serious cosmopolitan pest with with extensive host range of economically important crop such as cotton, groundnut, soyabean, tomato, sweet potato and many other crops. *S. litura* has been shown to be resistant to a wide range of insecticides, which had let to sporadic out breaks of the pest and failure of crops (Ahmad *et al.* 2007).

Since the pest was found in Hunan province of China, its damage has increased continuously. It's control has depended mostly on application of various insecticides. As a result, many field population of this pest have developed high resistance against wide variety of insecticides including organophosphate, carbamate, pyrethroids and some selected newer chemical insecticides with field control failure observed very frequently (Armes *et al.* 1997; Kranthi *et al.* 2001; Ahmad *et al.* 2007a, b, 2008; Saleem *et al.* 2008). In India, 32 different species of parasitoids have been reported as larval parasitoids of *S. litura*. Among these, *Apanteles* and *Bracon* sp. were the most commonly reported in 1974, Rai surveyed vegetable crops in the state of Karnataka and found that 10% of parval mortality was caused by *Chelonus formosanus* (Sonan). Battu (1977), during a survey of castor and cauliflower in the Punjab, found that *Parasarcophaga misera* (Walk) and *Campolitis* sp. also attack *S. litura* larvae.

The importance of the Neem tree has been recognised by the US National Academy of science, which published a report in 1992 entitled 'Neem- a tree for solving global problems'. Therefore, the use of neem leaf extracts could overcome this barrier towards tapping the good nutritional characteristics of neem leaf meal. The Neem leaves extract contains nimbin, 6-desacetylnimbiene, nimbandiol, nimbolide and quercetin (Mitra *et al.*, 2000)

Tulsi is believed "Queen Of Herbs "(Verma, 2016). The essential oil of Tulsi is extracted steam distillation from the leaves (Guenther, 1949 ; Simon *et al.* 1990)

Materials & Method

A. Experimental Insect:

Spodoptera litura (Fabricius) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) commonly called tobacco caterpillar or cutworm was selected for the proposed investigation. *Spodoptera litura* is a polyphagous pest of large host range including tobacco, cotton, cabbage, groundnut, maize, jute, lettuce etc.

For laboratory rearing the egg masses of *Spodoptera litura* were procured from Agricultural Research Station, Durgapura, and Jaipur. Rearing was done at the temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, $75 \pm 5\%$ RH and 10:14 hrs of Light:Dark period. The eggs were surface sterilized with 0.02% sodium hypochloride solution, dried and allowed to hatch.

B. Experimental Plant Material:

There is two plants namely, *Azadirachta indica* and *Ocimum sanctum* were selected for the evaluation of their insecticidal, growth regulating and behaviour disrupting activities against developmental stages and adults of *Spodoptera litura*. The ovicidal action of plants was evaluated by treating the eggs of *Spodoptera litura* with leaf extracts of *Azadirachta indica*, and *Ocimum sanctum* and seed extract of *Azadirachta indica*. Observations were taken daily till the larvae hatched out from the eggs.

Result and Discussion

1. *Azadirachta indica* Leaf Extract :

A massive discount in egg hatching used to be determined in eggs handled with the leaf extract of *Azadirachta indica* via each contact and egg-dipping strategies. Reduction in hatching used to be easiest of 87.08 percentage and lowest of 16.27 percentage when eggs have been handled through egg-dipping approach at 2% and 0.1% concentrations respectively.

When handled via contact technique eggs confirmed perfect discount of 86.36 percentage and lowest of 17.59 percentage at 2% and 0.1% concentrations respectively. Mortality in newly hatched larvae used to be recorded as 11.42, 15.33, 30.48, 58.18 and 66.66 percentage when eggs have been dealt with via contact technique and 16.98, 23.33, 33.23, 69.83 and 83.83 percentage when eggs have been handled by means of dipping technique at the concentrations of 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0% respectively.

Seed Extract: Maximum discount in egg hatching was once found when eggs have been dealt with through dipping approach at the attention of 2% (90.74). This used to be accompanied through a discount of 88.02 percentage at 2% when eggs had been dealt with by means of contact method. Minimum discount of 33.65 and 25.02 percentage in hatching used to be recorded at 0.1% awareness when eggs had been dealt with by using egg-dipping and contact techniques respectively. Mortality in the newly emerged larvae from dealt with eggs was once best of one hundred percent at 3% awareness in each sorts of treatments. At 0.1 percent of extract mortality in larvae was once recorded as 46.90 and 21.93 percentage in egg-dipping and contact redress respectively.

2. *Ocimum sanctum* Leaf Extract:

Maximum discount of 88.35% in egg hatching used to be found when eggs have been handled at the dose of 2.5% by means of egg-dipping technique and 87.33% discount in hatching of eggs passed off when dealt with by means of contact technique. Percent discount was once 15.23 and 14.33 in eggs uncovered to the awareness of 0.1% by using contact and egg-dipping techniques respectively. Percent mortality in newly hatched larvae was once sixty-eight and 72.22 at 2.5% extract when eggs had been handled via contact and dipping techniques of cure respectively.

Discussion

The consequences exhibit that all the two vegetation triggered mortality in the eggs, on the other hand the efficacy of flowers varied.

Results bought in current investigation exhibit that seed extract of Neem was once most wonderful and precipitated easiest mortality in dealt with eggs. Leaf extract of *A. indica* used to be additionally effective, although the ovicidal impact was once barely much less than the seed extract. The learn about found that extracts of neem and bakain brought about most unfavourable outcomes on egg laying capacity and hatching when the adults had been fed on extract containing sucrose diets. Their effects confirmed that egg laying used to be totally inhibited at the concentrations of 6, eight and 10% neem extract concentrations. Similar outcomes had been acquired in the current work the place two percent seed extract of *A. indica* induced 94.66 percentage egg mortality.

Ocimum sanctum confirmed average ovicidal recreation towards *S.litura*. Leaf and seed extracts evaluated in the existing learn about triggered mortality in the newly emerged larvae. Highest mortality inside forty eight hours of hatching used to be located in larvae emerged from eggs handled with leaf and seed extracts of *A.indica* at the attention of 2%(83.82 and 99% respectively). *Ocimum sanctum* confirmed reasonable mortality in hatched larvae. Death in newly emerged larvae may additionally be due to feebly sclerotised cuticle which leads to penetration of extract in larval physique main to toxicity and additionally outcomes in aborted hatching.

Conclusion

The effects it is proven that extracts of plant leaves and seed *A. indica*, and *O. sanctum* are exceedingly high quality in opposition to *Spodoptera litura*, an essential agricultural pest. Although azadirachtin, the energetic compound remoted from *Azadirachta indica* have been efficiently commercialized as an bio pesticide, however countless elements such as quick furnish of uncooked cloth of neem fruits, excessive price of isolation, opportunity of resistance improvement due to non-stop use, subject in its synthesis due to its complicated shape etc. make it economically much less desirable.

High efficiency proven by means of crude extract endorse that though azadiracht in content material is low in crude extract however different chemical compounds current exhibit cumulative impact and exhibit excessive insecticidal, increase regulating and behaviour disrupting things to do.

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